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***Corresponding
Author: Dr. Devidas
Thosar,**
Department of AI &
AIML, G.H.Raisoni
College of Engineering &
Management Wagholi,
Pune Maharashtra

Smart PPT Presentation: Using Hand Gestures

**Dr. Devidas Thosar¹, Sanika Arkile², Triveeni
Suryawansh³, Shweta Lilhare⁴, Renuka Vakhare⁵**

¹Assistant Professor, ^{2,3}Second Year B.Tech Students,
^{4,5}Assistant Professor,

Department of AI & AIML, G.H.Raisoni College of
Engineering & Management Wagholi, Pune Maharashtra

ABSTRACT

Traditional computer systems depend heavily on physical input devices such as a mouse and keyboard for interaction. While these devices are effective, they have several limitations including hardware dependency, wear and tear, hygiene issues in shared environments, and limited accessibility for physically challenged users. This project presents a Hand Gesture Controlled System that enables users to interact with computers using hand movements captured through a webcam. The system uses Computer Vision and Machine Learning algorithms to detect, track, and interpret hand gestures in real-time. By recognizing specific gestures, the system can perform actions such as cursor movement, clicking, scrolling, and volume control without any physical contact. The proposed system provides a touchless, cost-effective, and user-friendly alternative to traditional input devices. It is especially useful in smart environments, public systems, medical facilities, and situations where maintaining hygiene is essential. This technology enhances accessibility and represents a step forward in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI).

Keywords:-Hand gesture recognition, computer vision, opencv, mediapipe, virtual mouse, real-time detection, human-computer interaction (hci), touchless interface, machine learning, gesture-based control. [4,8,11]

1. INTRODUCTION

The aim of this project is to develop a Hand Gesture Controlled System that enables users to interact with a computer through simple hand movements, eliminating the need for traditional input devices like a mouse and keyboard. Conventional systems depend on physical hardware, which can lead to wear and tear, hygiene concerns in shared environments, and limited accessibility for differently-abled users. [8,11]

To overcome these limitations, the proposed system integrates Computer

Vision techniques, along with OpenCV and MediaPipe Hand Tracking, to detect and analyse hand gestures in real time using a webcam. The system tracks finger positions and recognizes predefined gestures to perform operations such as cursor movement, clicking, scrolling, and volume adjustment. [1,9,10]

By providing a touchless and intuitive interface, the system enhances convenience, improves accessibility, and represents a significant step forward in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). [4],[8]

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Table 1:-Literature review summary

Sr. No.	Paper Title	Publisher and Published Year	Methodology	Limitations
01.	OpenCV Library	Dr. Dobb’s Journal, 2000	Used OpenCV for real-time object detection and tracking.	Limited advanced AI features in early versions.
02.	Deep Learning-Based Hand Gesture Recognition Using CNN	IEEE, 2019	Applied CNN models for accurate gesture classification.	Requires large dataset and high processing power.
03.	Kinect-Based Gesture Recognition for HCI	IEEE, 2015	Used Kinect depth sensor for gesture tracking.	Needs special hardware; expensive system.
04.	MediaPipe Hands: Real-Time Hand Tracking	Google Research, 2020	Detected 21 hand landmarks using a lightweight ML model.	Performance decreases in low-light conditions
05.	Vision-Based HCI Systems: A Survey	Springer, 2018	Reviewed camera-based interaction techniques	Mostly theoretical; limited practical implementation

3. DRAWBACKS AND LIMITATIONS

Lighting Dependency

The system relies heavily on camera-based vision input. Poor lighting conditions, shadows, or backlighting can significantly reduce hand detection accuracy. [4,9]

Background Interference

Complex or cluttered backgrounds may introduce noise in hand segmentation, leading to false gesture recognition. [4]

Limited Gesture Vocabulary:

The system supports only a predefined set of gestures. Expanding gesture sets increases computational complexity and misclassification risk. [11]

User Fatigue (Gorilla Arm Effect):

Prolonged use of mid-air hand gestures can cause physical strain, making the system unsuitable for long-duration interaction. [8]

Occlusion Issues:

Overlapping fingers or partial hand visibility can degrade landmark detection accuracy. [4], [9]

Accuracy Trade-off Without Depth Sensors:

Since the system uses a standard RGB webcam instead of depth sensors, precise 3D hand positioning is limited. [5]

Objectives:

1. To design a touchless presentation control system using hand gestures. [8]
2. To detect and track hand landmarks in real time using computer vision techniques. [4], [9]
3. To map predefined gestures to PowerPoint control commands. [8], [11]
4. To improve accessibility and user convenience in presentation environments. [8]
5. To analyze system performance and identify practical limitations. [4]

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed Hand Gesture Controlled System operates by capturing live video

input through a webcam and processing it in real time. Each video frame is analysed using Computer Vision techniques to detect the presence of a hand. The system utilizes MediaPipe Hands to identify and track 21 key hand landmark points, including fingertips and joints. These landmarks help determine the position and movement of fingers accurately. [9]

Based on the relative positions and distances between these landmarks, predefined gestures are recognized using OpenCV and machine learning techniques. Once a gesture is identified, it is mapped to specific computer commands such as cursor movement, clicking, scrolling, or volume control. The corresponding command is then executed instantly, enabling smooth and touchless interaction. Overall, the methodology ensures real-time performance, accuracy, and efficiency, providing a cost-effective and user-friendly alternative to traditional input devices while enhancing Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). [1], [2],

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system captures live video using a webcam and processes each frame using computer vision techniques. MediaPipe detects 21 hand landmarks to track finger movements. The extracted features are analyzed to recognize predefined gestures. These gestures are then mapped to PowerPoint commands such as next slide, previous slide, and pointer control, enabling touchless presentation interaction.

Fig.1:-System Architecture of smart PPT Presentation

6. ALGORITHM

Step 1: Start the system, initialize the webcam, and set a suitable frame rate.

Step 2: Capture a frame and resize it to a fixed resolution.

Step 3: Detect the hand using a landmark model that identifies key points like fingertips and joints.

Step 4: Extract the (x, y) coordinates of the index finger and thumb.

Step 5: Calculate the distance between selected fingers; if it is less than a predefined threshold, recognize it as a click action.

Step 6: Map fingertip coordinates proportionally to the screen resolution.

Step 7: Perform the corresponding mouse operation (move, click, scroll, or drag).

Step 8: Repeat the process until the user exits the system.

7. MODULE-WISE DESCRIPTION

The proposed Smart PPT Presentation system is designed using a modular approach to ensure clarity, real-time performance, and ease of implementation. Each module performs a specific function

in the overall hand gesture recognition and presentation control process.

Video Capture Module

The Video Capture Module is responsible for acquiring real-time video input using a standard webcam. The captured video stream is divided into individual frames, which are resized and pre processed to ensure consistent input quality. Color space conversion is applied to improve hand detection accuracy. This module acts as the primary interface between the physical hand movements and the digital processing pipeline. [4]

Hand Detection and Landmark Extraction Module:

This module detects the presence of a human hand within each video frame and extracts key landmark points using a machine learning-based hand tracking model. A total of 21 landmarks representing finger tips, joints, and palm regions are identified. These landmarks provide a structured representation of the

hand, enabling accurate tracking of finger positions and movements in real time. [9]

Feature Extraction Module:

The Feature Extraction Module processes the detected landmarks to compute meaningful geometric features such as distances between fingers, finger orientation, and relative finger positions. These features help differentiate between various gestures. Normalization techniques are applied to reduce the impact of hand size and camera distance variations, ensuring consistent performance across different users. [4]

Gesture Recognition Module:

The Gesture Recognition Module classifies hand gestures based on extracted features. Predefined gesture rules and threshold values are used to recognize specific gestures such as slide navigation, pointer movement, or selection actions. Temporal consistency checks are included to minimize false detections and improve recognition accuracy during continuous hand movement. [2], [3], [7]

Gesture-to-Command Mapping Module:

Once a gesture is recognized, it is mapped to a corresponding presentation control command. This module establishes a logical connection between human gestures and PowerPoint actions such as next slide, previous slide, or pointer control. The mapping is designed to be intuitive, allowing users to control presentations naturally without prior training. [8]

Coordinate Mapping and Smoothing Module:

This module converts hand landmark coordinates from camera space to screen space. Proportional scaling is applied based on screen resolution. To reduce jitter and ensure smooth pointer movement, basic smoothing techniques are used. This

improves overall interaction stability and enhances user experience during presentations. [4]

Command Execution Module:

The Command Execution Module interfaces with the operating system to execute presentation commands in real time. It simulates keyboard or mouse actions required to control the presentation software. Visual feedback such as landmark display helps users understand system responses and adjust gestures accordingly. [1], [10]

8. EXPECTED OUTCOME

The expected outcome of the Smart PPT Presentation using Hand Gesture Controlled System is the successful implementation of a real-time, touchless computer control interface using only a webcam. The system is expected to accurately detect and track 21 hand landmarks, recognize predefined gestures, and convert them into corresponding mouse operations such as cursor movement, left and right click, scrolling, drag and drop, and volume control. It should provide smooth and responsive interaction with minimal delay, ensuring efficient performance.

The project aims to eliminate the dependency on traditional input devices like a mouse, promoting a contactless and hygienic computing environment. Additionally, it is expected to enhance accessibility for physically challenged users and serve as a cost-effective solution without requiring special hardware. Overall, the system contributes to the advancement of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) by offering an innovative, intelligent, and user-friendly gesture-based control mechanism. [8], [9], [11]

9. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Hand Gesture Controlled System presents an innovative

and efficient approach to human-computer interaction by replacing traditional input devices with a touchless interface. By utilizing Computer Vision techniques along with MediaPipe and OpenCV, the system successfully detects and tracks hand landmarks in real time and converts gestures into meaningful computer commands.

The project demonstrates smooth cursor control, accurate gesture recognition, and responsive system performance without requiring additional hardware. It enhances hygiene, improves accessibility for differently-abled users, and provides a cost-effective solution for modern smart environments.

Overall, this system represents a significant step toward intelligent, AI-driven interaction technologies and showcases the future potential of gesture-based computing in various real-world applications. [4], [8], [9], [10]

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